

LABORATORY TEST FIXTURE FOR
NON-RIGID PAYLOADS

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Abstract

Payloads associated with chemical munition projectiles often include liquids or other non-rigid compositions. This situation allows the payload to assume a relative motion to that of the projectile and can exert moments which may seriously degrade the projectile's flight stability. The Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads allows payload arrangements to undergo the simultaneous spinning and coning motions experienced by a projectile in flight. The fixture enables the destabilizing phenomena associated with the non-rigid payload to be created in a controlled laboratory environment where special instrumentation can measure the physical effects of interest. The results are used to evaluate the potential destabilizing influence of the payload and to support the evolution and validation of theoretical analyses describing the associated fluid dynamics situation. This paper describes the operational aspects of the fixture and reviews several research and development projects for which it has been employed. Engineering design aspects of the XM761 and M825 Smoke Screening Projectiles will be described. In addition, the role played by the fixture in evolving a general theory for homogeneous viscous liquid fills will be reviewed. Finally, studies associated with payloads composed of viscoelastic fluids and other unconventional compositions will be addressed including methods of reducing or eliminating the problem.

Symbols

AR canister aspect ratio (c/a)
 a canister inside radius
 C_{LSM} linearized liquid side moment coefficient
 $(M_{LSM}/\Omega \omega' a^2 m_L \sin\theta)$
 C'_{LSM} generalized liquid side moment coefficient
 $(M_{LSM}/\Omega^2 a^2 m_L \tan\theta)$
 C'_{LRM} generalized liquid rolling moment coefficient
 $(M_{LRM}/\Omega^2 a^2 m_L \tan\theta)$
 C_{LRM} linearized liquid rolling moment coefficient
 $(M_{LRM}/\Omega \omega' a^2 m_L \sin^2\theta)$

C canister inside half length
 I axial moment of inertia of empty canister
 I' axial moment of inertia of filled canister
 I_0 fixture moment of inertia - about coning axis
 I_0^* effective fixture moment of inertia
 I_T transverse moment of inertia of empty canister
 M_{FRM} friction rolling moment
 M_{FSM} friction coning moment
 M_{FSM}^* effective coning friction
 M_{LRM} liquid rolling (despin) moment
 M_{LSM} liquid side (yawing) moment
 m_L liquid mass
 P projectile spin rate
 R felt wedge radius
 R_0 Reynolds number based on ω
 $(\omega a^2/\nu)$
 R'_0 Reynolds number based on ω'
 $(\omega' a^2/\nu)$
 t time
 V total internal volume of container
 V_H volume of high viscosity fluid
 V_L volume of low viscosity fluid
 V' volume of fluid
 ω_N projectile nutation frequency
 α projectile angle of yaw
 θ coning angle
 ν kinematic viscosity

σ_N	relative coning angle of projectile in flight
r	non-dimensional coning rate (Ω/ω')
Ω	coning rate
ω	spin rate relative to coning reference frame
ω'	spin rate relative to inertial reference frame ($\omega + \Omega \cos \theta$)
γ	specific mass
$\dot{\gamma}$	shear rate

Introduction

The flight stability of spinning projectiles can be adversely affected by the internal movement of their non-rigid payloads. This is of particular concern to the U.S. Army Chemical Research, Development and Engineering Center (CRDEC) because many of the chemical projectile fills for both lethal agents and obscurants are non-rigid in composition.^{1,2} Two general types of instability can occur. One relates to low viscosity liquid fills where pressure waves created in the spinning liquid are in resonance with the projectile nutation frequency. This results in the liquid exerting a large moment which increases the projectile yaw angle in flight with a subsequent reduction in range and accuracy. The other type of instability involves highly viscous liquids and certain other partial solid/partial liquid non-rigid fills. In this instability, under the forcing of the nutation motion of the projectile, the liquid fill produces both a large yawing moment and a large despin moment. While the former "resonance" type of instability has been known and analyzed for some time, the latter "forced motion" instability was only identified fairly recently.³ Also, while these instabilities can be characterized for the extreme low and high viscosity liquid fill, there are intermediate viscosities where vestiges of both exist.

A special experimental apparatus has been extensively used to investigate the "forced motion" type of instability. These studies have included both pure liquid fills as well as various general "non-rigid" payload arrangements. The device, referred to as the Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads, forces a full sized payload container to undergo the simultaneous spinning and coning motions of a projectile in flight.⁴ The payload thus experiences the same inertial environment that it would have in flight, but under known and controlled conditions.

Various forms of instrumentation are employed to measure the different phenomena of interest. The most important have been the measurement of the despin and destabilizing yaw moments induced by the payload. Flow visualization techniques have also provided significant data. This paper reviews the use of this fixture in several experimental investigations which have provided an understanding of the

physics involved and contributed to the evolution and validation of theoretical analyses of this problem. Methods for predicting and eliminating the associated flight instabilities are also described and discussed.

Description of Test Fixture

The test fixture determines the effects of the payload or internal fill arrangement. Accordingly, only the payload container and its associated compartment constraints are required; the external projectile components are unnecessary. The fixture forces the payload container to undergo the simultaneous spinning and coning motion of the projectile in flight as illustrated in Figure 1. While the spinning projectile actually experiences an epicyclic motion consisting of both a low frequency precession and a fast frequency nutation, the nutation motion is the dominate effect. Thus, a simple, fixed angle coning motion of the spinning payload container is representative of the projectile motion in flight and the non-rigid payload experiences the same inertial environment as flight, but in a laboratory setting.

Fig. 1 - Relation of Flight and Fixture Motion

The Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads is shown in Figure 2. The various motion and moment terms are defined in Figure 3. A full sized cylindrical payload canister from a standard 155mm artillery projectile can be mounted between bearing housings attached to the rectangular frame. The bearings allow the canister to spin freely about its longitudinal axis simulating the spin rate of the projectile. The canister is spun by means of a high pressure air turbine located on the lower bearing housing. The canister can be set at selected angles to the vertical including 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 degrees. This represents the coning angle which corresponds to the projectile angle-of-yaw in flight. The frame, in turn, is mounted to a bearing arrangement located in the support table below. The coning motion which simulates the projectile nutation motion, is achieved by spinning the frame (with the canister set at the desired angle) about a vertical axis with an electric motor attached to the table. In addition to using actual munition payload canisters on the fixture, special cylindrical containers

can also be used to represent various internal cavity sizes and shapes desired for parametric studies.

Fig. 2 - Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads

The fixture can be operated at constant values of spin rate, coning rate and coning angle to simulate a particular flight condition. This approach was utilized in the several flow visualization studies conducted. The primary use of the fixture however, has been to measure the despin and yawing moments produced by the different payloads investigated. The payload induced despin (rolling) moment is particularly easy and accurate to measure on the fixture. After the payload canister is mounted to the fixture at the desired coning angle, the container is spun up to a spin rate of about 10,000 RPM while the frame is spun up to a specific predetermined coning rate. When both rotational rates are obtained, the air turbine is shut-off and the canister is allowed to despin while the fixed angle, fixed rate coning motion is maintained by the electric motor. The canister spin rate is recorded as a function of time by the data acquisition system as shown in Figure 4. This represents the basic measured data.

Data acquisition was accomplished by means of a Hewlett-Packard (HP) 9000-310 Technical Computer running HP Rocky Mountain BASIC, and a HP3852 Data Acquisition System containing a HP44715 5 Channel Counter/Totalizer Card. The HP9000-310 controlled all aspects of the data acquisition, storage, reduction and plotting. Magnetic sensors were used to measure the rotation rates. Canister spin rate was measured from the blades of the turbine providing twenty pulses per revolution. The table spin rate or coning rate was measured using four pulses per revolution. The operator monitored the two rotation rates displayed, in both graphical and digital formats, on the computer's CRT. When the appropriate test conditions were achieved, the operator initiated the data acquisition process by turning off the air to the turbine. The canister spin rate was then read every 0.8 second by the Counter Card and stored in computer

memory. The time was determined from the internal clock of the computer. Data acquisition was terminated when the selected lower limit of canister spin rate was reached. The data was then stored on flexible disc, reduced to liquid despin moments, and the results printed and plotted. The entire procedure for a specific coning angle and rate required about five minutes to complete.

Fig. 3 - Fixture Terminology

The computer converts the spin time history data to spin deceleration which is multiplied by the axial moment of inertia of the empty container (including any associated spinning bearing parts) to calculate the total despin moment acting on the container as a function of the canister spin rate. This total despin moment is

Fig. 4 - Typical Fixture Despin Data

due to only two effects: bearing friction and the internal payload. The friction moment is determined separately from similar tests with an empty container. Subtracting this friction moment from the total moment results in the rolling moment due to the payload. Figure 5 illustrates the resulting data from a typical test run with a viscous fluid-fill showing typical relative magnitudes of total, friction and payload moments.

Fig. 5 - Representative Fixture Moment Data

Similar test runs are then repeated at each coning angle for a range of coning rates. Combinations of spin rates, coning rates and coning angles can be simulated which correspond to actual projectile flight conditions. This provides an absolute measure of the rolling moment produced by the payload for flight conditions of interest. In other instances, the data can be expressed in non-dimensional form as a moment coefficient, coning rate and Reynolds number. The moment is actually measured for a non-steady condition in that the spin rate is changing and consequently the non-dimensional coning rate and Reynolds number are non-steady. However, the change in spin rate is relatively small and the resulting data, show good correlation with steady-state theoretical and numerical calculations.

Because of the presence of spin and the associated gyroscopic effects on the projectile flight dynamics, the moment induced by the liquid fill that actually causes the flight instability acts on the projectile in a yawing or sideward sense. As shown in Figure 6, this yaw or side moment tends to rotate the payload container out of the plan of the coning angle. While initially, the magnitude of the rolling moment was only considered as a qualified indication of the corresponding yawing moment, a general relation now exists between the liquid induced despin and yawing moments.

$$M_{LSM} = M_{LRM} / \tan \theta$$

This simple expression allows the destabilizing yawing moment to be computed from the experimentally determined despin moment which can be measured relatively easily and accurately on the fixture. Figure 7 illustrates the side moment computed from the measured rolling moment for the previous viscous liquid example. Thus, the fixture is limited to the "forced motion" types of instabilities associated with the high viscosity liquids or partial liquid/partial solid payloads because of the despin moment present.

NOTE: x y z ORTHOGONAL BODY AXES
 x PARALLEL TO SPIN AXIS
 y NORMAL TO ANGLE OF ATTACK PLANE
 z NORMAL TO x AND y AXES

Fig. 6 - Projectile Moments

Fig. 7 - Liquid Side Moment Relation to Liquid Rolling Moment

Partial Liquid/Partial Solid Payloads

The fixture was initially conceived to address a flight stability problem experienced during development of the XM761, 155mm screening artillery projectile development project. An early version of the fixture was built specifically to test full sized payload canisters from this projectile which contained numerous cotton wicks saturated with liquid white phosphorous. This partial solid/partial liquid fill had the composition of a "wet mop" and produced severe flight instabilities characterized by a simultaneous projectile yaw growth and despin as illustrated in Figure 8. After successfully demonstrating that the payload effect could be recreated on the fixture and measured through the despin moment, extensive studies were conducted to identify the critical phenomena creating the flight instability. Alternate payload configurations were evaluated on the fixture until a redesigned payload was established which eliminated the problem. The cotton wicks were replaced with felt wedges and the projectile redesignated M825 as illustrated in Figure 9. These felt wedges served the same function as the wicks, but their tighter and more controlled packing in the existing cruciform longitudinal baffle reduced the destabilizing moment sufficiently to produce a stable projectile flight.

Fig. 8 - Unstable Flight Motion of XM761 Projectile

For flight stability screening evaluations, the payload induced despin moment is measured on

the fixture at various coning angles for a specific spin and coning rate corresponding to the critical transonic flight motion conditions of the projectile. The graph of this despin moment versus the coning angle equates to the despin moment produced by the payload at these flight conditions for any projectile yaw angle. A stability boundary line can be drawn on this graph which depends on the inherent aerodynamic and gyroscopic (i.e., aeroballistic) stability of the projectile. The stability criteria is based on the typically large initial yaw angle experienced by the projectile after exiting the gun barrel at these transonic velocities. If the payload induced despin moment at this angle is below the boundary, the projectile's aeroballistic characteristics are sufficient to sustain a stable flight. However, if the payload despin moment is above the boundary at this angle, the payload moment will dominate and an unstable flight will occur. Currently, this boundary is established empirically from flight tests of the projectile with different payloads and is used with the payload despin moment for convenience. Eventually, this criteria could be presented as the yawing moment versus yaw angle and could be predicted from the detailed aerodynamic characteristics of the projectile.

Fig. 9 - XM761 and M825 Payload Arrangements

Recently, the fixture has been used to access the effect of production changes on the flight stability of the M825.⁶ Figure 10 shows the effect of increasing the packing density of the felt wedges and compares axial packing (i.e., adding additional felt wedges to stack) with radial packing (i.e., increasing the lateral dimension of the felt wedge). These data revealed the greater importance of lateral compression compared with axial compression in reducing the destabilizing effect.

The ability of the fixture to evaluate actual, payload canisters with their production flaws, imbalances, etc. provides a valuable tool in accessing the flight stability of complex payloads. This provides information and confidence that can not be achieved with specially fabricated models and scaling techniques. Also, after being tested on the fixture, the same payload can be loaded into a projectile and test fired from a gun.

Fig. 10 - Effect of M825 Felt Wedge Compression

High Viscosity, Homogenous Liquid-Fills

While still involved in the XM761 program, a series of experiments were conducted on the fixture with right circular cylinders (representing generic payload compartments) containing homogeneous liquids with a large range of viscosities. Natural fluids were selected which provided viscosity values over seven orders of magnitude and encompassing all possible fluid fills. The liquid fill induced moments measured were found to have similar characteristics to those obtained with the partial solid/partial liquid payloads of the XM761 and M825. The most profound result of these experiments, shown in

Figure 11, is that the despin moment increases with increasing viscosity, reaching a maximum at a viscosity of about 100,000 CS and then decreases with increasing viscosity. These data related to typical artillery projectile payload configurations and motion and revealed a potential source of flight instability not anticipated nor predicted by the then existing theories. These findings were subsequently confirmed by full scale, instrumented flight tests of projectiles having the same payloads. Flight data for a typical viscous liquid filled projectile is shown in Figure 12 illustrating its similarity to the partial solid/partial liquid XM761 projectile. This represented the first recognition of the "forced motion" type of liquid-fill flight instability. Various theoretical and numerical analyses have been performed to develop an understanding and predictive capability for this phenomenon. The fixture has played a key role in providing experimental data to support the evolution and validation of these theories.^{8,9,10,11,12,13}

There are currently two basic non-dimensional liquid-fill induced moment coefficient formulation in common use as defined in Figure 13. As can be seen, the coefficients are a function of the coning rate, spin rate, liquid mass, canister radius, canister aspect ratio and coning angle. One is termed the "linearized" coefficient and the other is referred to as the "generalized" coefficient. For a given cylindrical aspect ratio, the "linearized" coefficient is a function of the Reynolds number and also a linear function of the non-dimensional coning rate. This latter relation restricts this coefficient to small values of coning angle. The liquid side moment coefficient is equal to the negative of the liquid rolling moment coefficient. The liquid side and liquid rolling moments are related by the sine of the coning angle. The "generalized" moment coefficient is only a function of the Reynolds number for a given, cylinder aspect ratio. It's non-linear nature results in the yawing and rolling moments being related by the tangent of the coning angle. The liquid side moment coefficient is also equal to the negative of the liquid rolling moment coefficient.

An extensive series of experiments were conducted on the fixture to validate these coefficients and their respective theories.^{14,15} Silicone fluids (Dow Corning 200 Series Damping Fluids) having specific kinematic viscosities were used in these tests.

Figure 14 presents an example of the liquid roll moment as a function of spin rate for various constant coning angles. Dividing these moments by $\tan^2 \theta$ reduces the data to a single curve as shown in Figure 15. Similarly reduced moment data for a constant coning angle is shown as a function of spin rate for different coning rates in Figure 16. When these data are divided by Ω^2 , they also collapse into a single curve as contained in Figure 17. These examples illustrate the validity and value of these moment coefficient formulations.

The effect of canister radius was evaluated by adding a plastic insert sleeve into the ex-

Fig. 11 - Despin Moment Versus Liquid Fill Viscosity

Fig. 12 - Unstable Flight Motion of Viscous Liquid Filled Projectile

Fig. 13 - Definition of Liquid Moment Coefficients

isting cylinder which reduced the cylinder internal radius. End spacers were also added to reduce the internal length to retain the same aspect ratio with a consequent reduction in volume and liquid mass. Figure 18 shows the test fixture experimental data for the nominal and reduced radius cylinders filled with 100K CS fluid. The data shown are for a representative coning rate and coning angle condition. If these rolling moments are divided by the respective radii squared and the corresponding liquid masses, the data convert to a single curve as shown in Figure 19. The data are plotted against Reynolds number which is also a function of the cylinder radius. These results verify the effect of both the radius squared and liquid mass (i.e., constant liquid density, but different volumes) terms common to both moment coefficient formulations.

Fig. 14 - Liquid Moment vs Spin Rate and Coning Angle

Fig. 17 - Influence of Coning Rate

Fig. 15 - Influence of Coning Angle

Fig. 18 - Liquid Moment vs Spin Rate for Different Radii and Mass

Fig. 16 - Liquid Moment vs Spin Rate and Coning Rate

Fig. 19 - Influence of Radii and Mass

Another objective of this study was to determine the moment coefficient values over a large range of Reynolds number. Silicone fluids having viscosities of 1K, 10K, 60K, 100K, 300K and 600K CS were used. Each liquid viscosity only covers a limited range of Reynolds number and non-dimensional coning rate for the spin and coning motions considered in these experiments. Figure 20 depicts the linearized moment coefficient for the nominal cylinder filled with a 100K CS liquid. As can be seen, only data for a Reynolds number range from 5 to 20 were obtained for this particular liquid viscosity. It should be noted that typical spin stabilized projectiles have τ values between .05 and .2. Therefore, the data are shown for this range of τ . As expected, the coefficient is linear with τ , whereas the generalized coefficient shown in Figure 21 for the same test conditions, is independent of τ . Figure 22 illustrates the ability of the "generalized" coefficient to collapse the multi-curved "linearized" coefficients into a single curve which is only a function of Reynolds number. Finally, Figure 23 compares the generalized rolling moment coefficient obtained in these experiments with those computed by various theoretical means. As can be seen, agreement is quite good down to a log R of 1.5 (i.e., $R = 30$). Below this, the theories underpredict the moment. The influence of viscoelastic properties of the silicone fluids used in the experiments is currently being investigated.

Fig. 20 - Linearized Moment Coefficients

Unified Theory

Theories for the high viscosity liquid-fills can be combined with the established low viscosity fluid-filled theories to present a three-dimensional picture of the entire liquid-fill stability situation as shown in Figure 24.¹⁶ This plot shows the liquid-fill-induced linearized side moment coefficient as a function of the Reynolds number (representing the liquid characteristics) and the ratio of coning to spinning frequencies (representing the projectile motion) for a given cylindrical payload container length to diameter ratio. This approach graphically depicts the entire range of conditions including both the low and high

Fig. 21 - Generalized Moment Coefficients

viscosity regions corresponding to high and low Reynolds numbers, respectively. Of particular note is the presence of a large peak moment acting over a narrow frequency ratio range at the higher Reynolds numbers where inertial effects dominate and the large moment occurring over a broad frequency range in the viscosity dominated, low Reynolds number region. Sections through this plot represent trends for constant conditions. For example, for constant frequency ratios, the dependence of the liquid side moment coefficient on the Reynolds number is similar to Miller's experimental and Herbert's theoretical results for high viscosity fluids. The side moment coefficient, as a function of frequency ratio for constant Reynolds numbers, indicates trends similar to free gyroscopic experiments and Murphy's theoretical results for low viscosity fluids. The current objective is to establish a single or "unified" theory which can be applied for all Newtonian fluid situations. This will be used, in conjunction with a simplified Six Degree-of-Freedom (6-DOF) trajectory computer program, to design and analyze the flight performance of any flight vehicle. The use of the "generalized" coefficient makes this plot even simpler reducing it from three to two dimensions.

Measurement of Liquid-Yaw Moment

The fixture had been initially built under the assumption that the liquid induced rolling and yawing moments were manifestations of the same effect, but their exact relationship was not known at the time. If a large despin moment were measured, it was considered to be evidence that a large destabilizing yawing moment also existed. An experiment was conducted on the fixture to directly measure this yawing moment. The test technique used was similar to that used to measure the despin moment in that the yawing moment was measured by allowing the canister coning rate to decelerate and using these data to compute the liquid yawing moment. The test procedure was to have the liquid filled container simultaneously decone and despin at a fixed coning angle from a range of initial conditions. As seen from Figure 3, the liquid induced yawing moment has a component directed along the fixture coning axis. This component influences the coning deceleration of the fixture and can be determined using the following experimental technique.

Fig. 22 - Comparison of Linear and Generalized Moment Coefficients

The total coning moment is the product of the coning deceleration and a term representing the "effective" fixture moment of inertia about the coning axis. The expression for the liquid induced yawing moment is only a function of the net coning moment and the effective coning bearing friction moment. The effective coning bearing friction moment was determined from calibration runs using a canister containing a solid fill having the same weight as the liquid fill. The results of the experiment which were conducted with a representative, highly viscous liquid fill are contained in Figure 25.

These results demonstrated that a yawing moment was, in fact, produced by the liquid fill which was directed such as to be destabilizing to a spinning projectile. Also, a direct relation between the rolling and yawing moment was established.

Flow Visualization Studies

Although only limited flow visualization studies of viscous liquids in a spinning and nutating environment have been conducted to date, they have provided meaningful and sometimes surprising data.¹⁸

Fig. 23 - Comparison of Experimental and Theoretical Results

Fig. 24 - "Unified Theory" Plot

The first series of tests used an early test fixture design and provided insight into the internal flow field by investigating the distortion of a 5 percent air void in a viscous liquid filled, transparent cylinder under simultaneous spinning and coning motion. Spark photography and high speed film revealed that the void assumed a sinusoidal-like distortion as shown in Figure 26. While the distortion increased with increasing coning rate and angle, curiously, the void distortion remained essentially in the plane of the coning angle. These results indicated that the internal flow field was significantly different between low viscosity and high viscosity liquids and, surprisingly, the distortion disappeared with increasing liquid viscosity. The data were important to both the Vaughn and Herbert analyses.

The first flow visualization experiments involving the detailed flow field of a highly viscous liquid in a spinning and coning cylinder were conducted to compare the fluid motion with the results of a numerical analysis being per-

Fig. 25 - Liquid Yawing and Rolling Moment Measurements

formed by Sandia National Laboratories.¹⁸ A small number of neutrally buoyant beads were distributed throughout the transparent canister which was completely filled with a silicone fluid of known density and viscosity. A high speed camera located to the side of the fixture filmed the relative motion of the beads while the analysis procedure was to follow a single bead and denote its longitudinal position in the canister when the canister coning plane is normal to the viewing camera. When plotted over several coning cycles, the bead motion was determined to be constrained to a plane canted at a slight, fixed angle to the canister coning axis. Further, the bead motion undergoes a slight lag each cycle, producing the tangential shear stress and consequent despin moment. The results of this flow visualization test, although limited in scope, were vital to interpreting and validating the Sandia numerical solution of this complex fluid dynamic situation.

Fig. 26 - Void Distortion Experiment

Viscoelastic Fluids

While the major effort on this problem has been directed toward Newtonian fluids, future chemical agents are being considered which include polymer additives intended to improve the delivery efficiency of the munition. The combination of agent and polymer results in a non-Newtonian or viscoelastic fluid whose viscosity is dependent on the shear rate imposed on the fluid. Typical "thickened agent" fluids are found to be "shear-thinning" because their viscosity decreases with increasing shear rate. An experimental study was conducted to investigate the destabilizing characteristics of a shear-thinning viscoelastic fluid payload in a spin stabilized artillery projectile application.¹⁹ These data were compared with corresponding data for Newtonian fluids with regard to creating a liquid fill induced flight stability. For artillery projectile applications, the most severe problem occurs for liquids having kinematic viscosities on the ord-

er of 100,000 CS. Typical agent/polymer solutions possess a zero shear viscosity of about 1,000 CS to 10,000 CS at standard day temperatures. Under cold temperature operations, the viscoelastic liquids have viscosities similar to that of the high viscosity Newtonian fluids which are known to produce flight instabilities. For this study, a viscoelastic fluid was specially prepared to provide the nominal 100,000 CS zero shear rate viscosity at ambient room temperature. Its shear thinning properties are shown in Figure 27.

Figure 28 compares the despin moments for the non-Newtonian and Newtonian fluids having similar zero shear viscosities of about 100,000 CS for the same nominal motion conditions. Note that the viscoelastic fluid has a slightly larger maximum despin moment which occurs at a lower spin rate than the Newtonian fluid. However, the moment decreases significantly at the higher spin rates corresponding to actual projectile spin values. Figure 28 also compares the non-Newtonian fluid with a Newtonian fluid having a viscosity of 1,000 CS or about two orders of magnitude lower than that of the other Newtonian fluid. As can be seen, the despin moments are very similar. Evidently, under the action of the spinning and coning canister, the liquid experiences such large shear rates that its effective viscosity is reduced two orders of magnitude and the liquid acts as if it were a Newtonian fluid with a greatly reduced viscosity, and a correspondingly reduced moment.

Effect of Partial Fill

Considerable progress has been made in understanding and analyzing the flight dynamics of spinning projectiles having highly viscous liquid fills. However, these techniques are limited to completely filled, right circular cylinders. A series of experiments were conducted using the Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads to measure the despin moment produced by a viscous liquid in a partially-filled cylindrical container undergoing simultaneous spinning and coning motion. The resulting data can be used to evolve and validate theoretical analysis involving a partial-fill condition.²⁰ The canister was evaluated at fill ratios (V'/V) of 1.0, 0.98, 0.95, 0.90, 0.80, 0.70, 0.60, 0.50, 0.40, 0.30 and 0.20 for various coning rates with the canister coning angle constant at 20 degrees.

Figure 29 shows the liquid rolling moment plotted against the canister spin rate for various fill-ratios under a constant coning angle and rate of 20 degrees and 500 RPM, respectively. This is the largest value of coning rate evaluated and produced the largest moments. Also shown are the non-dimensional coning rates associated with these test conditions. Note the general clustering of the curves for fill ratios of 0.7 and above.

The liquid-fill induced rolling moment can be expressed as a non-dimensional coefficient which is only a function of Reynolds number. These coefficients are shown plotted against fill-ratio in Figure 30. Experimental data using liquids of 100,000 CS was selected to

Fig. 27 - Viscosity vs Shear Rate

provide data in the Reynolds number range around ten thus, encompassing the peak moment value. Since the coefficients include a liquid mass term in the denominator, a reduction in liquid tends to increase the coefficient even though the moment produced might be the same. The effect of the liquid mass can be removed by multiplying the coefficient by the fill-ratio as shown in Figure 31 for constant values of Reynolds number. This plot illustrates the true effect of the partial fill induced moment. This plot shows that the maximum moment does not occur at the maximum fill condition, but at a partial fill condition just before the moment abruptly decreases.

Fig. 28 - Liquid Roll Moment vs Spin Rate for Viscoelastic and Newtonian Fluids

Fig. 29 - Liquid Roll Moment vs Spin Rate for Various Fill Ratios

This leads to the surprising observation that for typical artillery projectile flight conditions, (i.e., $\tau = .1$), the liquid induced destabilizing moment is relatively insensitive to the amount of liquid fill present (around the condition of maximum liquid carried desired for a munition system). In fact, the large destabilizing moment present for the completely filled canister remains at a large value even when as much as 50 percent of the liquid is removed!

Fig. 30 - Liquid Rolling Moment Coefficient vs Fill-Ratio for Various Reynolds Numbers

Fig. 31 - Destabilizing Moment Due to Partial-Fill

Elimination of Viscous Liquid-Fill Flight Instability

As noted previously, homogenous, liquid fills can create severe flight instabilities in spinning projectiles. In the case of a low viscosity liquid, the familiar "resonance" type instability can be eliminated by minor changes in the aspect ratio of the internal compartment (i.e., length to diameter ratio). For the "forced motion" type instability associated with highly viscous liquids, changing the aspect ratio has little effect. Accordingly, alternate means are being considered to reduce or eliminate this type of instability. A series of experiments were completed on the Laboratory Test Fixture for Non-rigid Payloads to evaluate the effect of adding a small amount (1-2 percent by volume) of an immiscible, low viscosity fluid to the highly viscous liquid fill in order to reduce or eliminate the destabilizing moment.²¹

A cylindrical container was initially filled 98 percent by volume with a silicone fluid having a specific viscosity of 100,000 CS and a specific mass of .98. This particular viscosity was selected because it produces the maximum destabilizing moment (for the artillery projectile application) of any homogeneous, viscous liquid. The liquid fill induced despin moment was measured for the typical fixture spinning and coning rates at coning angles of 10 and 20 degrees. This provided a reference fill condition to allow comparison with the influence of the lower viscosity, immiscible fluid additive.

Water was used as the low viscosity, immiscible liquid additive. In addition to being immiscible in the silicone fluid, it possesses a much lower specific viscosity (1 CS) and has a slightly larger specific density. The container of 100K CS fluid was evaluated with various amounts of water with the ratio of the volume of water (V_w) to the volume of silicone fluid (V_s) evaluated for values of 0, .01, .02, .05 and .10 fill conditions.

Figure 32 shows the liquid induced moment measured for the various percentages of water as a function of the container spin rate for a specific value of coning rate and coning angle.

Fig. 32 - Effect of Low Viscosity, Immiscible Additive to Reduce Viscous Liquid Moment

Of particular interest, is the moment which occurs at a spin rate of 6,000 RPM. This condition relates to an actual artillery projectile transonic flight condition where the aerodynamic stability of the projectile is minimal and the liquid-fill induced moment can produce a flight instability. Note that, a water amount of .02 results in a significant reduction in the despin moment and consequently, the yawing moment. The effect of the density of the low viscosity, immiscible additive was investigated by using alcohol in place of the water. The alcohol possesses the same viscosity as the water, but had a slightly lower density than that of the 100,000 CS fluid. Similar tests to those done with the water were conducted with the alcohol and the 100,000 CS silicone fluid in various amounts. This arrangement did not alter the liquid induced despin moment at all. Thus, for the rotating container situation, the low viscosity additive must have a larger density than the main high viscosity payload because the centrifugal effect dominates the situation.

Fig. 33 - Influence of Low Viscosity, Immiscible Additive

The experiments were repeated using a 10,000 CS silicone fluid with water as the low viscosity additive. The 10,000 CS fluid does not produce as large a moment as the 100,000 CS fluid for identical motion conditions. However, the fractional reduction in the moment due to various amounts of low viscosity additive is similar as shown in Figure 33. Thus, the use of a low viscosity, immiscible fluid additive has the po-

tential to decrease the liquid induced moment for a range of realistic liquid fills.

The immiscible, low viscosity liquid additive appears to have the same general effect in reducing the liquid induced moment as that observed with a shear thinning, viscoelastic fluid as also shown in Figure 32. Instrumented flight tests, of full scale artillery projectiles are planned to verify this finding.

Conclusions

1. Although a relatively simple device, the Test Fixture for Non-Rigid Payloads has provided key experimental data toward understanding and establishing a theoretical basis for the destabilizing effect of viscous liquid-fills and non-rigid payloads in spinning projectiles.
2. Because of its ability to evaluate actual, full size, munition payload configurations, the fixture provides a means of assessing the flight stability potential of complex partial liquid/partial solid payloads which can not be easily or confidently scaled down.
3. The fixture provided the first experimental evidence of the existence of a destabilizing phenomena due to highly viscous liquid-fills and established the first qualitative and quantitative analysis of its characteristics.
4. Flow visualization studies on the fixture have allowed valuable insight into the internal fluid motion which have been very beneficial to understanding the phenomena involved.
5. The first laboratory measurement of the liquid-fill induced destabilizing yawing moment and verification of its relation to the liquid-fill induced rolling moment were obtained on the fixture.
6. Extensive studies on the fixture have validated both the linearized and generalized liquid moment coefficients and established an experimental data base for their relation with Reynolds number for both complete and partial fill conditions.
7. The effect of the severe motion environment in dramatically reducing the apparent viscosity of shear thinning, viscoelastic fluids was first observed through fixture experiments.
8. A means for reducing or eliminating viscous liquid-fill flight instabilities was demonstrated on the fixture which involves the addition of a small amount of an immiscible, low viscosity liquid.

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